

MODELING OF THE SKIN PROPERTIES OF 3D FABRIC SANDWICH COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Sandwich panels are used when the combination of light weight and high bending stiffness is demanded. The biggest disadvantage of the existing materials is their poor impact and delamination resistance. Sandwich panels based on 3D-fabrics, in which top and bottom skin are interconnected, can solve these problems. In this paper, a model is proposed to describe the elastic behavior of the skin material. It is based on the Fabric Geometry Model (FGM). Based on the geometry of the skins, a unit cell is defined. The unit cell is split up in smaller subcells, of which the stiffness matrix is calculated, based on a 3-dimensional laminated plate theory. Special subcells, containing the pile fibres, were developed. Summation for all subcells allows the calculation of the elastic constants of the skin. A parameter study was performed to investigate the changes in orientation of warp and weft bundles, fibre volume fraction and their influence on the elastic constants of the fabric.

keywords: sandwich panel, 3D-fabric, Fabric Geometry Model

1. INTRODUCTION

The most important property of composites is the combination of low weight, and excellent mechanical properties. However, full composite panels for big structural elements, are often too expensive and too heavy, especially because these panels are mainly loaded in bending. Therefore, special composite sandwich panels have been designed. They are made of strong and stiff skins (e.g. fabrics), and a very light core material. As core materials, foams and honeycombs have become common use.

These sandwich panels have some major disadvantages. First, the cost of a honeycomb structure is rather high. This renders the panels too expensive for some applications (automotive and marine industry). Second, these sandwich panels are very delamination sensitive: minor impacts can cause a delamination between the skin and core material or core failure. Bending or compressive loads will lead to delamination growth and stability problems of the panels.

The existing problems can be solved by connecting the skins to the core, so no delamination can occur. This is achieved by using three-dimensional fabrics (figure 1), produced by Parabeam. Interconnecting "pile threads" are co-woven with the upper and lower skin in a one-step velvet weaving process. This connection between top and bottom skin will result in a higher delamination resistance.

Results of some mechanical evaluation on 3D-fabric sandwich panels, have been published earlier [1,2,3], showing that the 3D sandwich panels have properties, equal to or even higher than the honeycomb material. Only the bending stiffness is lower, due to shear deformation of the core. However, new types of 3D-fabrics are being developed to improve the shear stiffness of the core.

For a better understanding of the material behavior, the development of a model describing the elastic behavior of the sandwich panel is necessary. The model is split up into two parts: one for the core and

Figure 1: Schematic view of a 3D-fabric: the two skins are interconnected by pile yarns in a one step weaving process.

one for the skin. This paper focuses on the skin properties. The model presented here, can easily be adapted to other fabric types.

2. FABRIC GEOMETRY MODEL

In the past, many different models have been developed to model the strength and stiffness of 2- and 3-dimensional fabrics [4]. The Fabric Geometry Model (FGM) was first developed by D. Whyte et al. [5] and extended by D. Liao [6] to describe the elastic behavior of 3D-braided composites loaded in compression. The model has also been used on other fabric types [7,8].

It can be split up in the following phases:

1. Based on the fabric geometry, a unit cell describing the complete fabric, is defined. Figure 2 presents the very simple example of a plain weave.
2. The unit cell is split up into different subcells. Each subcell describes the geometric path of one fibre bundle. Each square in figure 2 hence represents four subcells: two for the warp, and two for the weft yarn. The elastic constants of each subcell are calculated.
3. The elasticity matrix of the unit cell is obtained by summation of the elasticity matrices of all the different subcells.

The model uses two basic assumptions. Each fibre bundle is treated as a unidirectional laminate. The matrix is assumed to be isotropic, whereas the fibre is assumed to be transversely isotropic. The elasticity matrix of one fibre bundle is obtained, taking into account the fibre and matrix properties, and the fibre volume fraction within the bundle. The elasticity matrix of one subcell is obtained by taking into account the yarn orientation in the subcell.

The unit cell elasticity matrix is calculated as the sum of the elasticity matrices of all the subcells. This means that all the yarns are assumed to be parallel. This should lead to an overestimation of the properties, because the stronger subcells are dominating. Nevertheless, previous results have shown good correlation with experimental data.

The Fabric Geometry Model was chosen because of its flexibility, allowing the description for many different fabric types, from simple plain weaves to satin weaves and other complex structures. It also allows the determination of the strength of fabrics. However, the work presented in this paper is limited to the calculation of the elasticity matrix.

Figure 2: Unit cell description of a plain weave fabric. Each square is split up into four subcells: two for the warp, and two for the weft yarn.

3. SOLUTION SEQUENCE

3.1 Definition of the unit cell

The 3D-fabric has a more complex structure than the regular woven fabrics, because of the presence of the pile yarns in the skin fabrics. Based upon the weaving pattern, the unit cell can be defined. An example unit cell is presented in figure 3. The unit cell is identical for both top and bottom skins.

Figure 3: unit cell of an example 3D-fabric. The shaded areas are places where the pile yarn is not present: it is in the core or in the other skin.

3.2 Description of the subcells.

The next phase of the model is the development of the subcells, based upon the black-and-white image, presented in figure 3. Different subcell types are necessary to describe the fabric. For each subcell, it is necessary to accurately describe the yarn geometry. Some assumptions have been made:

- The yarn tension is assumed to be sufficient to obtain straight yarn paths.
- Each bundle is assumed to have a racetrack shape (cfr. figure 5), and is defined by the width w and the thickness t .
- The distance between the bundles is assumed to be constant. In this way, the pick lengths in the warp and weft direction p_w and p_f can be defined.
- The fibre bundles are a densely packed composite. Two different packing factors can be used (figure 4). In the case of circular packing, a fibre volume fraction of 75 % is reached. For a hexagonal packing, a maximum of 91 % can be reached.

Figure 4: The two different assumptions for the fibre packing within a yarn, used in the present analysis.

The different subcells, two of which are shown in figure 5, can now be defined. The first subcell (fig. 5a) describes a warp bundle which goes from left to right over the weft yarn, which is cut in half. The warp yarn path can be described mathematically, based on the assumptions and on some geometric parameters which have to be used as input for the model. The following parameters are obtained by examining a cut and polished impregnated fabric: the yarn circularity f , defined as:

$$f = \frac{t + w}{t} \tag{1}$$

in which t and w are the yarn thickness and width; the skin thickness D ; the pick length p_f ; the excen-

Figure 5: Some examples of subcells. The subcell on the left describes the path of a warp yarn. The subcell on the right describes the entry of a pile bundle into the skin. A racetrack shape is assumed for the different bundles. The parameters which describe the yarn geometry are presented.

tricity parameter h_f , describing the distance between the yarn center and the center of the skin. From these input parameters, the warp and weft yarn thickness t and width w (both yarns are identical), and the dimensions of the pile yarn t_p , w_p are calculated. The warp yarn angle β_w is obtained by:

$$\beta_w = \text{Arc cos} \left(\frac{t_w + t_f}{h_f} \cos \left(\text{Arc tan} \left(\frac{p_f - w_f}{h_f} \right) \right) \right) + \text{Arc tan} \left(\frac{p_f - w_f}{h_f} \right) \quad (2)$$

Subcells describing the weft yarn path are defined in a similar way.

The pile yarn subcells are the same as the warp yarn subcells, except for the yarn dimensions. However, some special subcells have to be defined, describing the entry or exit of a pile bundle (fig. 5b). A pile exit (or entry) angle β_p has to be measured to fully define the yarn path.

$$V_{\text{warp}} = \left(w_w t_w + \frac{\pi t_w^2}{4} \right) \left(\frac{w_f}{2} + \beta_w \left(\frac{t_w + t_f}{2} \right) \right) + \frac{1}{\cos \beta_w} \left(\frac{p_f - w_f}{2} \right) - \tan \beta_w \left(\frac{t_w + t_f}{2} \right) \quad (3)$$

For further calculations, it is important to know the volume of a yarn in the subcell. Based upon the geometry of the yarn, this volume can be calculated. For figure 5a, the yarn volume is given by: A library containing different subcells, has been set up to enable the description of different 2D- and 3D-fabrics. A software program has been written to determine, from the black-and white image, which types (and how many) subcells are necessary to describe the unit cell.

3.3. Calculation of the elasticity matrix.

To calculate the elasticity matrix of one subcell, the following parameters have to be known:

- the fibre (E_{f1} , E_{f2} , G_{f12} , G_{f23} , ν_{f12}) and matrix (E_m , G_m , ν_m) properties;
- the unit cell type and the geometric parameters mentioned above;
- the fibre volume fraction, obtained by equations like eq. 3;
- the 3-dimensional stiffness matrix of the yarn, obtained using rules of mixture.

The yarn orientation is taken into account by using a transformation matrix:

$$[C]_{\text{subcell}} = [T]^T [C]_{\text{yarn}} [T] \quad (4)$$

in which $[T]$ is the transformation matrix, an example of which is:

$$\begin{bmatrix} m^2 & 0 & n^2 & 0 & -mn & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ n^2 & 0 & m^2 & 0 & mn & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & m & 0 & n \\ 2mn & 0 & -2mn & 0 & m^2 - n^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -n & 0 & m \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

Table 1: input data, used in the model.

E_m (GPa)	3.5	diameter pile fibre (mm)	0.009	diameter warp/weft fibre (mm)	0.011
G_m (GPa)	1.25	# filaments pile	400	# filaments warp/weft	600
ν_m	0.33	β_p (°)	50	pick length weft (mm)	1
E_f (GPa)	71	skin thickness (mm)	0.4	pick length warp (mm)	1
G_f (GPa)	30	ν_f	0.22		

Table 2: chosen parameter values for f , h_f and K . The numbers in the first row are used in figures 6, 7 and 8.

parameters	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
packing factor K	0.75	0.91	0.75	0.91	0.75	0.91	0.75	0.91
excentricity h_f	0	0	0	0	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
circularity f	1	1	4	4	1	1	4	4

in which $m = \cos \beta$ and $n = \sin \beta$.

The elasticity of the unit cell (and thus of the skin) is obtained by:

$$[C]_{\text{unit cell}} = \sum \frac{N_{\text{subcell}}}{N} [C]_{\text{subcell}} \quad (6)$$

With N the total number of subcells, and N_{subcell} the number of times a certain subcell type is present.

4. RESULTS

Based on the analysis presented in paragraph 3, a parameter study was performed. The input values have been brought together in table 1. The influence of the packing factor, the excentricity parameter h_f , and the bundle circularity f , were investigated. The chosen values are presented in table 2.

The fabric geometry and the elasticity matrix was calculated for the example unit cell in figure 3, and for the plain fabric, presented in figure 2.

Figure 6 presents the change in orientation of the warp and weft bundles in both fabric types. It can be seen from figure 6a, that the warp angle is identical for both fabric types. The packing factor has an influence on the bundle dimensions (compare even and odd categories in figure 6): a high packing factor results in a thinner yarn bundle, and thus smaller yarn angles. It is obvious that circular bundles result in higher angles than the racetrack shape which is the more realistic (compare categories 1 and 3, 2 and 4, etc). The most important parameter is the excentricity factor (compare the first four with the last four categories). If $h_f = 0$, then the weft bundle is completely straight (figure 6b). This value is not realistic, because the warp yarns are stressed during the weaving process. This load results in a much lower warp angle, as can be seen from columns 7 and 8 in figure 6a. As can be seen from figure 6b, a small difference is found for the two fabric types. Due to the presence of the thinner pile bundles, the weft angles are somewhat smaller.

From the subcell dimensions, the fibre volume fractions can be calculated, if one assumes that the entire subcell is filled, either by bundles or by epoxy resin. For the plain weave, a value of 30 % is found. For the 3D-fabric, 25.5 % is found. Both values are very low. This can be explained by two

Figure 6: orientation of the warp (a) and weft (b) bundles in the plain and the example 3D-fabric.

effects. First, the real bundle is lense shaped, which results in a lower fabric thickness and less free space in the subcells. Second, the assumption that the free space of the subcells is filled by resin is not valid. Both effects lead to an underestimation of the volume fraction. The lower value of the 3D-fabric is caused by the presence of the pile fibres: the pile subcells have the same dimensions as the warp subcells, but the volume fraction is lower, because of the smaller dimensions of the pile yarn.

The fibre volume fraction has an important influence on the elastic constants, as can be seen from figures 7 and 8. The difference between the two fabrics is caused by the difference in fibre volume fraction. From figure 7a, the influence of the yarn orientation can be seen: as the warp yarn angle decreases, a distinct increase of the stiffness can be found. The same conclusion can be drawn from figure 6b for the weft yarn. For categories 7 and 8, it can be seen that the fibre volume effect between the two fabrics is almost completely compensated by the lower angle for the 3D-fabric. A decrease in elastic properties in the warp direction results in an increase in the weft direction and vice versa (cfr. fig. 7). Both effects compensate each other when the shear modulus is envisaged (figure 8).

From a practical point of view, categories 7 and 8 are the most important. For these two conditions, the elastic constants have been calculated for a real 3D-fabric (the unit cell is not presented). The moduli in the warp and weft directions were found to be 19 and 16, respectively, showing a higher stiffness than both fabrics presented in this paper. The higher stiffness is caused by the special weaving type, used for all the different 3D-fabrics.

Figure 7: E-modulus (a) in the warp direction, E_1 , and (b) weft direction, E_2 , for both fabric types and the different parameters presented in table 2.

Figure 8: In-plane shear modulus of the different fabrics.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the Fabric Geometry Model was used to determine the elastic constants of different types of 2D- and 3D-fabrics. Special subcells were developed to take into account the pile bundles in the top and bottom fabric.

To describe the bundle geometry, both a circular and a racetrack shape were used. It was shown that the racetrack shape is the more realistic, although a lense shaped bundle would be even more realistic.

A parameter study was performed on an example 3D-fabric and a plain weave. The results show that the choice of the bundle shape and the bundle excentricity have an important influence on the yarn angles, and thus on the stiffness in warp and weft direction. The shear moduli are not influenced by these parameters. Apart from the bundle orientation, the fibre volume fraction has to be taken into account: a loosely woven fabric will have low warp and weft angles, but also a low volume fraction, resulting in a lower stiffness than a densely woven fabric. It was found that the fibre volume fraction of the 3D-fabric was lower than the plain weave, resulting in a lower stiffness.

Further research is going on to optimize the models, presented in this paper, and to implement strength calculations for the different fabrics.

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